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The Moon Cycle: A Critical Menstrual Studies Perspective of Select Novels

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Abstract:

This paper studies one of women's pressing issues in recent times, menstruation, around which spirited discussions and campaigns have converged. It explores literary representations of menstruation and menstruators using critical menstrual studies perspective. Anita Diamant's *The Red Tent* (1997) and Aida Salazar's *The Moon Within* (2019) have been selected for analysis. This paper explores the ways in which the two novels portray women's lived experiences of menstruation. Furthermore, it examines and questions the validity of several stereotypes, popular myths and beliefs constructed around it. It also comments on the various cultural practices and menarche rituals depicted in the select novels. It concludes by suggesting that menstrual justice is crucial in achieving gender equality.

Keywords: Menstruation, Menstruators, Critical menstrual studies, *The Red Tent*, *The Moon Within*, Stigma.

'Woman' has been the subject of discussion of every other discourse in the universe, invariably by those who are not women, from time immemorial. Varied aspects of women's lives and experiences have been discussed, investigated, examined, defined, constructed and narrated in the discourses of their 'other' sex, and most often the images created by such

discourses are misleading, distorted and monstrously untrue. Many of women's experiences are either mystified and glorified or stigmatized and devalued. But since women have broken the spell of silence and grasped the power of articulation, they have not just reclaimed their lived experiences but have redefined and reconstructed them in newer and positive ways too. Despite contesting and engaging with age-old belief systems and institutions, traditions and world views such as women's natural inferiority, their sexual autonomy and pleasure, marriage, pregnancy, abortion, childbirth, motherhood, rape, pornography and practices like child marriage, dowry and sati, women's discourses have still not paid enough attention to some of their issues. One such occasionally discussed subject is menstruation, a mundane reality of the majority of women's lives. Literature too has not thrown much light on it except for in young adult and teen literature like Judy Blume's novels and appropriate literary representations of it are not easy to find. Even though candid discussions of it have started popping up in recent times, its various implications and dimensions, particularly when it combines and intersects with other factors and issues, needs closer examination. Hence this research paper studies literary representations of menstruation and its implications.

This research paper aims to use critical menstruation studies as the theoretical framework to study the select novels. It aims to examine the ways in which different groups of menstruators experience the phenomenon of menstruation in their everyday lives and how their lived experiences of it are represented in the novels chosen for analysis. It also attempts to demystify the phenomenon by examining the myths, popular beliefs and fictions constructed around it. Furthermore, it explores how menstruation is embedded in a network of power structures, religious and cultural practices and age-old ancestral traditions and critically analyses and questions them. Finally, it states the importance of nurturing the right attitude towards menstruation.

This research paper has chosen two novels for study. The novels are Anita Diamant's *The Red Tent* (1997) and Aida Salazar's *The Moon Within* (2019). Diamant's *The Red Tent* is a revisionist historical fiction. It narrates the story of the almost forgotten biblical character, Dinah, the only daughter of Jacob and Leah in *Genesis*. It recounts her relationship with her mother and half-mothers and their lives together in the red tent. *The Moon Within* is the coming-of-age story of the twelve-year-old Puerto Rican-Mexican Celestina Rivera and her gender fluid friend Magda Sanchez. It describes how both Celestina and Magda come to terms with their bodies and their natural processes.

This research paper, as mentioned earlier, employs the critical menstrual studies, a recent and burgeoning field of theory and enquiry to examine the selected novels. The term 'critical menstruation studies' or critical menstrual studies was coined by the feminist historian Sharra L. Vostral and *The Palgrave Handbook of Critical Menstruation Studies*, to which she has contributed, is the first of its kind to discuss menstruation as a wide-ranging field of enquiry. Chris Bobel, one of the editors of this handbook, observes that critical menstruation studies looks at the new lines of enquiry, research questions and justice engagements that can be made possible when menstruation becomes the focus of study. This field treats menstruation "as a dynamic category of analysis", examining how systems of power and knowledge are built upon the understanding of menstruation (Bobel 3). As Bobel notes, it is a "coherent", multidimensional, transdisciplinary subject of "enquiry and advocacy" that is capable of both constructing epistemologies and bringing about social transformation (4). It examines the political, social, cultural, medical and biological constructions of menstruation and how it can be studied across disciplines such as policy-making, public health, art, gender studies, nursing, anthropology, sociology, psychology, communication studies and history. Menstruation is as old as the human race itself. For many feminist historians and anthropologists, the first woman's evolution from oestrus to monthly menstruation was a crucial moment for the human

race as it ensured its survival without becoming extinct. For feminist historian Rosalind Miles, this evolution gave the human race 60% more chances of reproduction than the higher primates. In her book *The Women's History of the World* (1988) and its updated reprint in the US *Who Cooked the Last Supper? The Women's History of the World* (2001), she argues that it was menstruation, not hunting, that was the greatest “evolutionary leap forward” for the human race (24). She notes, by referring to Penelope Shuttle and Peter Redgrove’s proposition in their book *The Wise Wound: Menstruation and Everywoman*, that menstruation is not just another physiological function like eating and defecating as it was responsible for the development of the mental capabilities of the human race. It cured its “mental darkness” she writes (24). When women began to notice the connection between their monthly body cycle and the lunar cycle, for the first time they learnt to make associations, understand abstractions, numbers, symbols and calendar organization, as their bodies themselves carried an inbuilt biological calendar. The discovery of a reindeer bone with thirty-one scratches on it is for Miles a record of a woman’s intimate life. But such an important phenomenon has gone “unsung”, “unmentioned” and unnoticed and no record of it is found in majority of the anthropological and historical works (25). Alma Gottlieb and Buckley Thomas’s *Blood Magic: The Anthropology of Menstruation* (1989) is one of the first full length feminist anthropological studies about it. In this scenario, the emerging field of critical menstruation studies gains significance as it explores the real “lived experiences” of menstruators (Winkler 12). It investigates how a wide range of factors such as religion, culture, socialization, political systems, caste, disability, beliefs and norms and power shape this lived experience and subsequently, examines the ensuing gender inequality, the tension between the private and the public, the processes of racialization and commodification, practices and discourses of embodiment and emerging menstrual products and technologies (Bobel 5; Winkler 12). Taking all these into consideration, this paper looks at representations of menstruation in literature.

The very title of Diamant's book is significant. The red tent is the women's space, the space where the women of Laban's tribe gather for everything from menarche to child birth. Dinah, the narrator of the book, refers to it as "the menstrual tent" (3). Its colour itself indicates its connection to blood, women's blood. Dinah informs the readers that this tent has been witness to her mother and her mother-aunties' transition into womanhood, their escapades as young women and their chronicles of child birth. The women of Laban's tribe, both his kin and slave women, withdrew from work at the commencement of their monthly cycle and retired to this tent where they told stories, sang songs, wove clothes, offered three-cornered cakes to the moon and most of all supported each other. Such a tent was strictly forbidden to men. However, the concept of the red tent among the Mesopotamians and Sumerians, where Laban is believed to have lived, around 1500 B.C itself is fictitious. Anita Diamant herself observes that she did not find any historical or biblical or Rabbinic evidences about the presence of a red tent ("Red"). She remarks in her interview with Sienna Brancato, "I did not find any evidence that women in this period of history in what is now Iraq and Israel used a menstrual tent. However, menstrual tents and huts are a common feature in pre-modern cultures around the world, from Native Americans to Africans." Alma Gottlieb confirms Diamant's accounts in her essay "Menstrual Taboos: Moving Beyond the Curse" by noting that some tribes of Polynesia, Africa, native America and South Asia used such a structure for menstruating women. Usually, several menstruating women gathered in an offside building and pursued arts and crafts and other relaxing activities. This offered them a female space for socializing, support and rest. Gottlieb remarks that such tents and huts become spaces for "contemplation, relaxation or spiritual renewal" (147). But she does not refer to any such practice among Jewish women and points out that only in the twentieth century a handful of ethnic Jews from Nigeria have brought this African practice into Israel (153). Aida Salazar's reference in her novel *The Moon Within* to red spatial menstrual huts, a space where Puerto Rican-Mexican women gathered to talk,

nurture, create and to feel connected to a sacred space, too lack ample historical evidence. It may perhaps have roots in oral traditions (86).

Another remarkable aspect of Diamant's novel is that all women enter and leave the red tent at the same time every month. Dinah observes that at the new moon, all the women commenced bleeding and at the appearance of the crescent moon, their bleeding stopped (29). Even though women have built-in biological clocks and calendars, it is impossible to ascertain if they could start menstruating on the same day. Such a phenomenon is called "period syncing" or "menstrual synchrony" or the "McClintock effect" (McDonald; "Period Syncing"). Martha McClintock studied the menstrual cycle of 135 women in an American college dorm and published her findings in the journal *Nature* in 1971.

She argued that the pheromones of women spending time together affected each other and they menstruated together. For her, it was a strategy that women had evolved over the years to protect themselves from becoming prey to predator males who could exploit them sexually. However, researchers today believe that this is only a popular myth or belief. Alexandra Alvergne, Associate Professor in Biocultural Anthropology at Oxford University remarks that period syncing is merely hypothetical and is nothing more than "randomness" (McDonald). A 2006 study which analyzed the menstrual cycles of 186 women living in groups in a Chinese dorm concluded that women do not sync their menstrual cycles and any such appearance is only "within the realm of mathematical coincidence" ("Period Syncing"). Another study of the menstrual cycles of 1500 women by Oxford University in collaboration with the period tracking app Clue writes off the chances of women disrupting each other's menstrual cycles by just living in close proximity ("Period Syncing"). Siddiqui et al. conclude their study of the monthly cycles of Indian medical students sharing community accommodation, by observing given the ideal conditions that they have similar age and similar stress patterns, sharing the same bed, food and emotions could result in period syncing, which is highly impossible in real

circumstances. So, the portrayal of all the women, including the slaves, entering the red tent at the same time is only fictitious. The women of Diamant's novel do not live under ideal conditions. They are not of the same age nor do they undergo the same levels of stress. All the wives of Jacob live and rest in separate quarters and cook their own meals. The fiction is carried too far when Diamant describes them carrying their red tent in their journey to Mamre and entering it together even during this exodus. Besides, the duration of menses varies from woman to woman and so the portrayal of Laban's women leaving the tent on the same day is also highly impossible.

Apart from menstrual synchrony with cohorts, Dinah's statement about all the women entering the red tent at the new moon indicates a lunar synchrony too. As observed earlier, women's recognition of this link between menstrual and lunar cycles, in Rosalind Miles's view, had been the first step towards human intellectual development. Not just Diamant, but Salazar too alludes to the connection between the moon and women's bodies in her novel. Celestina, or Celi, is fascinated by the moon and she calls it "luna" (6). Her mother Amelia calls periods the "moon" and when Celi protests by saying, "It's a period, mima, ... not a moon", she replies, "It will come every 29 days just like the moon. So, it's a moon cycle" (9). Furthermore, she points out that their ancestors had understood this connection and called the coming-of-age rituals "moon ceremony" (10). Salazar also adds to her novel a moon calendar created by cover artist Joe Cepeda, which would help women to trace their moon cycle, and "A Flower Song" translated from Spanish by David Bowles, which celebrates the connection between the moon and women's bodies. But unlike Diamant, the moon Salazar refers to is the full moon which is believed to be the sacred time among the Puerto Rican-Mexicans.

Regardless of the difference in the belief systems referred to in the two novels, the scientific evidence behind such claims ought to be examined. A 1986 study of the menstrual cycles of 826 women, aged sixteen to twenty-five, over four lunar months in different seasons, by Sung

Ping Law of the Department of Gynecology, Canton Traditional Chinese Medical College, clearly illustrates the association between menstrual and lunar cycles. One of the first of its kind, this study upheld Chinese traditional beliefs and concluded that large numbers of menstrual cycles synced with the new moon. But a handful of studies in the last decade contradict such a conclusion. For instance, a 2013 study of 980 menstrual cycles in 74 women over a calendar year found no link between the two cycles at all. The findings of the Clue app, a period tracking app, published in 2016, which is an outcome of the analysis of 7.5 million menstrual cycles of 1.5 million Clue users, showed similar results. However, a new study conducted by Professor Charlotte Helfrich-Forster and her team in the Neurobiological and Genetics Biocentre in the German University of Würzburg found intermittent synchrony of menstruation with two of the moon cycles. Published in 2021, the research studied the menstrual cycles of 22 participants for a period of 32 years and concluded that women's monthly cycles closely synced with the luminance and gravimetric cycles of the moon. Luminance cycle refers to the variation in the intensity of the moon's light as it changes its position to the sun and as it passes through different phases from new to full moon. On the other hand, gravimetric cycle refers to the varying force the moon exerts on earth as it moves in its elliptical orbit around it and the force differs according to the distance ("Do Menstrual"). Forster notes that the probability of menstrual cycle syncing with the cycles of the moon decreases as women age. Furthermore, she notes that this syncing is only intermittent even among young women, owing to the changes in their lifestyles, which have increasingly exposed them to artificial light. She remarks, "We hypothesize that in ancient times, human reproductive behaviour was synchronous with the moon, but that our modern lifestyle, notably our increasing exposure to artificial light, has changed this relation" ("Do Menstrual"; Jones).

This may be the reason why "A Flower Song" for maidens coming-of-age at the end of Salazar's novel describes maidens exposing themselves to the moonlight in a ritual occurring

near a stone pool in the middle of the woods. Their teacher and guide, an old woman, instructs them to do the following:

Remove your clothes.

Let down your hair.

Bask in the moonlight,

Naked as the day of your birth,

Virgins,

Maidens,

Women (228).

This song was written in the Middle Ages long before the encounter with the Europeans and was found in a collection of Yucatec Maya poems called Songs of Dzitbalcke. This song describes the link between human circadian and ecological rhythms. Besides, Forster's research suggests Diamant's portrayal of women having their periods at the new moon may be true as her novel is set in the biblical times, around 1500 B.C.

The attitudes the novels studied here present towards menarche and menstruants are also significant points to be examined. Menarche is a reality most girls have to face at some point in their lives. Alexandra J. Hawkey, Jane M. Ussher and Janette Perz note that it is a "symbolic" transition from childhood or girlhood to womanhood. It is a period of growth, change and sexual maturation (98). So, the sociocultural perceptions about menstruation and menstruants shape the menstruants' relationships to their bodies. Such perceptions have a grave impact on their psychology and self-esteem. Besides, Alma Gottlieb notes that menstruation is experienced by each individual and community in widely different ways as it is affected by political, religious, economic and demographic factors, in spite of it being a "shared biological"

aspect (144). Many societies, cultures and religions view it as impure, pollution, dirty, a taboo and curse, while some others regard it as sacred, powerful and magical (145). These world views are manifested in the menarche rituals or the rituals of the first blood. The two novels studied here portray some such rituals.

The *Old Testament*, on which *The Red Tent* is largely based, and the *Talmud*, the centre of Rabbinic Judaism, view menstruation as an impurity. Ilana Cohen refers to Chapter 15 of *Leviticus* and *Tractate Niddah* for such views (116). So, *The Red Tent* sends a paradoxical message about menstruation. While it latently drops rules to be followed during menstruation and shows Laban's household Gods, his teraphims, being defiled and losing power by Rachel's menstrual blood, it also celebrates menarche and menstruation as sacred and powerful. Rachel's menarche is described but very implicitly in the first part of *The Red Tent*. She has been eagerly waiting for this moment as she has already received Jacob's proposal for marriage and cannot marry before her first blood. Before leading her into the red tent, the magical space of womanhood, menstruation and childbirth, she is decked with jewels and embroidered cloth and is painted with henna. She is welcomed into the red tent with songs in praise of the pantheon of Goddesses like Innana, with sweet wine and delicious food and an aromatic massage which induces sleep. Her initiation into womanhood is completed when she is carried to the fields to be married to the earth. Her first blood is collected in a bronze bowl as the first blood of a virgin was believed to be a powerful "libation" for the garden (30). Rosalind Miles observes that this practice was common in many primitive cultures and the menstrual blood was regarded as a powerful fertilizer for the crops. She refers to the practice of soaking corn seeds in the menstrual blood before sowing in ancient Greece (43).

Dinah's menarche rituals described later are similar to Rachel's, but more detailed and graphic. Her first blood arrives in spring and she remarks that her "... childhood is over. I will wear an apron and cover my head" (202). For a moment, she considers keeping this a secret

but realizes that this is useless. She remarks, “I could only be what I was. And I was a woman” (203). She is welcomed into the community of women and is loved and supported by them. Constantly surrounded by them, they teach her the ways of women and she learns to appreciate her bodily changes and adjust the rhythms of her body to the phases of the moon. When her mother and her aunts apply henna to her feet and palms, decorate her with red lines and patterns of dots, deck her with jewels, perfume her head and armpits, massage her, give her a new gown and feed her, she feels pleased. “It was good to be a woman” she observes (203). Dinah is taken to the recently tilled wheat patch of her mother’s garden, where the grains used in sacrifice are grown and the “lock” of her “womb”, in Dinah’s words, is broken when Rachel inserts the narrow triangle of the smoothly oiled and polished frog-shaped Innana into her vagina (206). Her first blood too is collected and offered to earth with a prayer to Innana. But this must have been a primitive practice not a Jewish one as Jacob objects to it and destroys Rachel’s teraphims when he hears of such a nocturnal ritual from his daughters-in-law. However, he contradicts his own mother, Rebecca, the diviner, healer and prophet of Mamre, who had condemned Tabea’s mother for wasting Tabea’s first blood and for isolating her during that time. Tabea’s dreams are shattered when Rebecca refuses to accept her as her Debora for this same reason. Not only that, Tabea also receives Rebecca’s curse.

Dinah is neither surprised nor confused about her menarche because Leah has already prepared her mind on this matter at Mamre itself. She explains to Dinah that “the secret of blood”, menstruation, is Innana’s gift to women, about which men have no idea. She remarks, “The flow at the dark of the moon, the healing blood of the moon’s birth-to men, this is flux and distemper, bother and pain. They imagine we suffer and consider themselves lucky. .. In the red tent, the truth is known” (188). In the red tent, it is truly revered as it is the source of life. It cleanses women’s bodies, washing them of the previous month’s unborn life and preparing them to receive that month’s new life. That is why the birth of a daughter is celebrated

in Leah's tribe as the birth of a birth-giver. Leah further explains, since menstruation is Innana's gift, the first blood of a girl is returned to earth, her womb, from which both men and women were born. It is also the sacred business of women, not of men, to break the lock of women's wombs. But Jacob and many other tribes of Israel reject such a view. For instance, when Jacob demands bride-price from Hamor for giving Dinah away to his son Shalem in marriage, he remarks, "Your daughter is not a virgin, Jacob. ... Yet, here is a bride-price fit for a virgin princess of Egypt - more than my own father gave for my wife." (230-31). On hearing this Jacob demands an explanation from Leah and comments, "Your daughter is no longer a girl ... You were insolent to keep this from me" (231). He feels Leah has humiliated him by concealing the truth about his daughter's virginity. The conflict between the belief systems of Laban's tribes women and numerous other Israeli tribes including Jacob's suggests that virginity might have begun to surface as a physiological notion around that time. Feminists like Naomi Wolf opine that virginity and chastity are concepts contrived by patriarchy to restrict women's sexual autonomy and freedom of movement (2). Medical experts are of the view that virginity is not physical or biological, neither is it medical. It is merely a cultural and "social construct", remarks Sophia Smith Galer, the author of *Losing It*. She also observes that ascribing women's sexual history to a miniscule tissue in their body is an unfair and harmful practice. Despite discussing such hot issues, *The Red Tent* does not refer to the Jewish practices of niddah (seclusion) and miqvah (ritual bath).

Amelia, Celi's mother in Salazar's novel, like Leah, gradually prepares her daughter for her menarche. As an immigrant parent, she is determined to hand down her ancestral wisdom about menstruation to her daughter while imparting a modern outlook of her body. She calls her girl parts the "floor" and had taught her to wash them properly since she was very small. She had held a mirror between her legs and had asked her to inspect her girl parts. She had given names to each one of them like "button-pee", "the birth canal" and "happy button" (34-35). She

observes, “Our floors are women’s most magical parts, mija. Aren’t we lucky?” (34). She speaks to her daughter about the commencement of her first blood and the moon ceremony. As Hawkey et al. point out mothers’ attitude towards menarche and menstruation shape their daughters’ views of them (106). In this novel, Celi is hesitant in talking about her bodily changes to her mother, in spite of her mother’s positive outlook about menarche. She is defiant about the moon ceremony too as she does not want to share her secret with her community. Amelia informs her that as neither her mother nor her sisters had prepared her for her menstruation, she cried out of shame. “It came as a stain of blood so dark she thought she was sick” (85). She learns about the moon ceremony in the monthly meetings of her women’s circle, a space for dreaming, talking, creativity, letting out feelings and relaxation (50). Her wish to celebrate her daughter’s moon ceremony is not merely a way to rejoice in her maturing body and getting accepted into the circle of women. But it is a political act to revive her ancestral menarche rituals which were erased by the advent of the colonizers in the fifteenth century. Besides, her wish is also a gesture towards reclaiming women’s bodies and their natural functions, which were made dirty by them, something to be ashamed of and hated.

When Celi reaches puberty during a dress rehearsal for the summer Bamba performance at La Pena Centre, she is confused, embarrassed, uncertain, frightened and doubtful. She is confused because her body is bleeding without pain. She wonders if that is the power of women’s bodies. However, she continues to be diffident about the moon ceremony and only Amelia’s determined coaxing could make her prepare for it. Amelia makes it clear that she will not let her enter womanhood in doubt and shame and that she will be surrounded by strong women in their community. She says, “That is our way. ... It is a way that we have to reclaim so that we are not erased” (183). For Celi’s moon ceremony, an altar is built in their backyard and offerings are placed in all the four directions, which represent the four elements of nature. Mexican and Yoruba Gods and Goddesses are placed on the altar. Teresa and Amelia build the

ceremonial moon hut and a fire pit with ricks, which represents the thirteen moons in a year. All the women are given a glass jar of water to collect the moon's rays, which they can drink when they require healing. Before entering the women's circle, Celi's grandmother smears each one of them with copal incense and only then, Celi feels her divine feminine energy. The women honour her and accept her into their lineage of life givers. A necklace with twenty-nine black clay beads, which represent a God for each day, and eight moonstones interspersing them, which represent the eight phases of the moon in the lunar cycle, is placed around her neck. Like Dinah, she too offers her first blood to the earth, by pouring the basin of water, in which she is made to wash a piece of her underwear soaked by her first blood, into a pit. The women create a sisterhood by sharing stories and secrets about their menarche and menstruation and making her drink the moonbeam water from the glass jar. Celi feels loved and supported instead of feeling lonely and frightened. Magda/Marco, Celi's gender fluid friend, is afraid of menarche because they think that it would erase their boyhood and would continue to keep them a girl. But the circle of women accepts and honours them too because it is the way of their ancestors (184-228).

Menstrual management in the days of Leah and Rachel is another interesting detail that Diamant's novel describes. Diamant depicts her women as sitting on straw and rags spread on a mound of sand in the red tent. When they had to move around, they placed rags between their legs (42). Rachel is shown as sitting on her father's teraphims, his household gods, buried in her straw. On reaching her puberty, Dinah remarks, "I will idle with my mothers and my sisters in the ruddy shade of the red tent for three days and three nights, until the first sight of the crescent goddess. My blood will flow into the fresh straw, filling the air with the salty smell of women" (203). The women of Diamant's novel can be classified as what Gottlieb calls the "free bleeders" (153). Free bleeding refers to menstruating without using menstrual products to absorb or collect the flow (Sharkey; McSwiggan). When Gottlieb refers to free bleeding, she

discusses it as a tool to destigmatize menstruation. Indeed, free bleeding has become an activist movement in recent years to protest against higher taxation on menstrual products and their unaffordability (153; Sharkey; McSwiggan). But Diamant's description would lead one to surmise that perhaps menstrual products were not invented in the times of Leah and Rachel. However, the feminist historian Rosalind Miles points out that tampons or soft pads made out of leaves and menstrual slings or belts, along with the handbag, were one of the first inventions of the human race. She argues that if the first women were free bleeders, hiding in caves and sitting on heaps of leaves a quarter of every month, it would have been an immense loss to their groups as their productivity and labour would have been severely affected (25). Even though there is a gap in the historical records about menstrual products, it can be deduced from available sources that menstrual bandages were available in Ur Sumeria between 6000 and 1500 B.C, the period Diamant describes in her book ("Ancient"). So Diamant's portrayal of free bleeding women must be hypothetical.

Both *The Red Tent* and *The Moon Within* present varied messages to the readers. While *The Red Tent* celebrates menstruation and calls menstruators life givers, it also regards menstruation as impurity at some point. The novel's perception of menstruation is contradictory. Perhaps, Diamant was describing a period of transition when patriarchal values were gradually spreading. On the other hand, Salazar's novel *The Moon Within* offers a clear message, a message of acceptance and celebration of women's bodies. Besides, the red tent or the menstrual hut referred to in both the novels is necessary to create a specialised space where women could relax, talk, share, celebrate themselves, their womanhood and the bonding between them and to build sisterhood. However, if women are out of work for a certain period each month, for, women can have varying lengths of menstrual flow, from three to ten days, their value in the labour market may diminish. Patriarchy may use this as an occasion to deter their progress and to provide equal opportunities and a fair playing field. Furthermore,

menstrual huts mean seclusion and isolation and it might invite harm from men and wild animals. Moreover, if boys and men are to be sensitized about menstruation, it is no use hiding it and isolating women. Diamant's *The Red Tent* is a historical fiction, but many of the events are built on premises and surmises owing to lack of historical evidences regarding women's menstrual lives even in the *Bible*. On the other hand, Salazar's *The Moon Within* is quite practical even though there is a reference to the ancestral moon ceremony.

Perceptions of menstruation must change in order to create gender, body, social and menstrual justices. The United Nations in 2019 pointed out that “The stigma and shame generated by stereotypes around menstruation have severe impacts on all aspects of women's and girls' rights” including their right to equality, freedom of religion and belief, health, education, housing, water, sanitation, safe and healthy working conditions, the right to take part in cultural and public life. It views menstrual rights as fundamental to human rights (qtd in Winkler 10). So, menstruation should neither be made dirty and shameful nor be glorified and placed on a pedestal. It should be normalized as a natural biological process required for sexuality, reproduction and the perpetuation of the human race. Menstruation must be used as a critical point of enquiry to highlight injustices arising out of it like period poverty, entry into shrines, harmful menstrual products, the taxation on them, etc. Menstruation, like similar issues of women, is caught up in power politics and as Gloria Steinem observes, if only men could menstruate, it would become a virtue and sanitary products would be made available free of cost.

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